

Colonoscopy Pain Reaction Biopotential Database - CPRB

Steffen Walter

*Medical Psychology
University Clinic of Psychosomatic
Medicine and Psychotherapy
Ulm University
Ulm, Germany
ORCID: 0000-0001-7165-3541*

Sascha Gruss

*Medical Psychology
University Clinic of Psychosomatic
Medicine and Psychotherapy
Ulm University
Ulm, Germany
ORCID: 0000-0002-4846-6921*

Sebastian Goetze

*Department of Internal Medicine I
Ulm University
Ulm, Germany*

Philipp Werner

*Institute for Information
Technology and Communications
University of Magdeburg
Magdeburg, Germany
ORCID: 0000-0003-4762-2926*

Alexander Hann

*Department of Internal Medicine I
Ulm University
Ulm, Germany
ORCID: 0000-0001-8035-3559*

Abstract— Automated pain recognition (APR) is a method for the objective measurement of pain. The focus on APR is the computer-aided objective recognition of pain which is realized on the basis of machine learning. In recent years, several databases (BioVid, SenseEmotion, X-ITE pain) have been collected in the laboratory to test machine learning algorithm. Numerous publications have taken place. However, it is now relevant to test the algorithms on clinical data sets with highly structured clinical protocols. In this respect, we recorded multimodal physiological signals during colonoscopy. Furthermore, clinical triggers (pain [Behavioral Pain Scale], movements, paralinguistics, and Propofol injections) were recorded synchronously. The database enables machine learning methods to test and optimize pain recognition on clinical data. It is planned to make the dataset available to a broad community.

Keywords— *Automatic Pain Recognition, Machine Learning Methods, Translation, Colonoscopy*

I. INTRODUCTION

The diagnosis of pain in clinical medicine, as well as its measurement in human experimental research, is largely based on subjective assessments of patients. For many aspects of pain research and treatment this is insufficient and difficult, as Elliott [1] emphasizes. However, the methodology of pain measurement in medical and psychological diagnostics has so far only been solved to a limited extent, explicitly in people with limited communication skills (e.g. cognitive impairment). A less valid pain measurement can lead to misdiagnosis, depression, chronic pain and cardiovascular stress in high-risk patients. On the other hand, too high doses of painkillers are contraindicated as they lead to addictions and can have undesired side effects such as nausea and constipation. To assess the intensity of pain in people with impaired communication and/or consciousness, external monitoring instruments such as ZOPA [2] or BESD [3] are used. These are based on the categorization of sounds, facial expressions, gestures and physiological indicators, but require professional expertise and have the risk of perception- and interpretation-related misjudgments and do not permit continuous pain assessment.

The automated recognition of pain, which was investigated in the present study, is based on the recording of pain reactions, which are in principle based on the same pain

model.

In the recent decade, the validity of automated pain recognition procedures have been tested utilizing observation scales. To date, pain responses have been detected primarily on the basis of video data using machine learning methods [4]. In our own studies (see [5] [6], [7], [8]), recorded data sets based on heat pain using multimodal sensor technology (physiology, video, audio) (BioVid [9], SenseEmotion Database [10]). For the first time, Gruss et al. [5] extracted similarity characteristics from physiology and achieved a detection rate of 90.9% in distinguishing between baseline and pain tolerance using an SVM algorithm. From these results in the field of automated pain recognition, it can be concluded that the experimental methodology and high degree of standardization of heat pain stimulation have increased the construct validity, while accepting a simultaneous decrease in the ecological validity. Thiam et al. [11] achieved detection rates of 60-65% for the first time, based solely on paralinguistic parameters from the SenseEmotion Database. Walter et al. [7] showed that recognition rates resulting from multimodal fusions were significantly better than unimodal recognition rates in 70% of all individual tests. In 2018, we created a database (X-ITE Pain Database, [12]) containing two pain models (thermal vs. electrical) and different pain durations (phasic vs. tonic).

The BioVid Heat Pain Database is now available for the Affective Computing community and is used as a benchmark data set by a number of prominent research groups, e.g., Lopez-Martinez and Picard [13] at the MIT. Since no experimentally produced data sets with different pain stimulations (heat, pressure, and electrical stimuli) are yet available, the extent to which the promising results from heat pain stimulation can be transferred to other pain stimulations remains unknown.

Finally, clinical data sets are necessary to translate the laboratory résumé - of automated pain recognition - into a clinical application. A colonoscopy environment is suitable for this purpose.

Colonoscopy is a safe method to identify pathologies of the colon and the terminal ileum. In addition to chronic intestinal diseases such as ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, colorectal cancer screening is one of the most common indications. Although this type of examination can

be performed without sedation in the majority of cases, the patient's wish in clinical practice leads to sedation being performed in almost every case. To standardize this procedure, the "S3 Guideline for Sedation in Gastrointestinal Endoscopy" was published in 2015. It recommends that every patient should be offered sedation before endoscopy. Propofol is a sedative with minimal analgesic effect. The sedative effect of Propofol is based on the binding to GABA receptors. Propofol unfolds its effect within 30 to 45 seconds after application. After short-term continuous application for 30 to 60 minutes, the time until awakening is approx. 5 to 10 minutes.

II. CLINICAL PROTOCOL AND COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

A. Participants

98 participants (female = 47, male = 51), aged between 18 and 87 years ($M = 53.62$, $SD = 17.20$), participated in the experiment.

a) Inclusion criteria:

- a) Age ≥ 18 years
- b) Indication for colonoscopy
- c) Planned sedation with Propofol
- d) ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists): I (normal, otherwise healthy patient) and II (patient with mild general disease without performance impairment)

b) Exclusion criteria:

- a) Lack of written consent of the patient
- b) Pregnancy
- c) Sedation by an anesthesiologist necessary
- d) ASA: III (severe disease with limited performance) and greater

B. Clinical Protocol (Triggers)

- Propofol time and dose
- Paralinguistic noises (level 1, 2, 3)
- Movement (level 1, 2, 3)
- Observed pain based on the Behavior Pain Scale (level 1, 2, 3)

After examination of all inclusion and exclusion criteria, a written explanation of participation was provided. Biopotential sensors were attached before the intervention. The intervention took place as planned, independently of the study. The measurement was completely passive and did not influence the type or quantity of medication application. The colonoscopic intervention was part of the clinical routine.

During the intervention, no insight into the measured physiological values was possible for the clinical staff, which were additionally collected within the scope of the study. At the end of the endoscopy, all sensors were removed and the patient was discharged or transferred back to the ward after the usual monitoring time. This was done in accordance with the standards of endoscopy. The colonoscopies lasted between 11 minutes and several hours.

C. Measured Physiological Parameters

The following physiological signals were recorded at the rate of 2048 Hz, utilizing a Nexus-32 amplifier and the corresponding BioTrace-Software (www.mindmedia.com):

1) *Facial Electromyography (fEMG)*: Bipolar pairs of Ag/AgCl electrodes were utilized for measuring fEMG activity. The electrodes were placed over the right *corrugator supercilii* and *zygomaticus major* muscles. Electrical muscle activity indicates general psychophysiological arousal. In particular, a high level of muscle tension is an indicator of stress, which is also expected to occur under the experience of pain.

2) *Skin Conductance Level (SCL)*: Skin conductance is a measure of the conductivity of the skin, which especially increases if the skin becomes sweaty. To measure SCL, two electrodes were attached to the edge of the left hand. Electrodermal activity is considered a sensitive indicator of the inner tension of an individual.

3) *Electrocardiography (ECG)*: Three single Ag/AgCl electrodes were utilized to measure the average cardiac action potential on the skin. One electrode was placed on the chest, approximately 6 cm below the right collarbone. The second electrode was placed on the left lower rib cage. The third electrode served as reference and was attached to the right-side waist next to the pelvic bone. It also served as reference for the fEMG. Common features of the ECG signal are heart rate, interbeat interval and heart rate variability (HRV). Heart rate reflects emotional activity, whereas HRV refers to the oscillation of the interval between consecutive heartbeats and acts as an indicator of mental effort and stress.

4) *Skin Temperature (T)*: The temperature sensor was developed for monitoring very small temperature changes (up to 1/1000 degrees) in the peripheral extremities (in degrees Celsius or Fahrenheit). In this study, it was attached to the right little finger with a medical tape. Normally, a stress event, an excitation or an activity of the sympathetic nervous system causes a vasoconstriction in the peripheral extremities and thus a drop in temperature.

III. FIRST DESCRIPTIVE SIGNAL PROGRESSIONS

First visualizations and sight checks of the signal characteristics were performed in order to develop strategies in terms of signal processing, e.g. filtering, feature extraction and classification algorithms (Fig. 1).

IV. CONCLUSION AND PLANNED ANALYSES

The data set requests opportunity to detection mimic expression and to record sympathetic and parasympathetic regulation mechanisms on the other hand.

We plan to test:

- 1) Different methods of signal processing
- 2) A granular feature extraction and selection
- 3) Transfer learning between experimental datasets (BioVid, SenseEmotion, X-ITE pain) and CPRB dataset
- 4) Linear combinations of the recorded bio signals
- 5) Deep learning algorithms

The collected data is planned to be published for academic research purposes.

Fig. 1. Example of one patient: Biosignal (Skin Conductance Level, Electromyography: Corrugator and Zygomaticus, Temperature [hand surface]) courses via *pain* triggers on the left and via *Propofol* injections on the right side (1 min before and 1 min after the event). All signals shown here were filtered and averaged.

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